

A Study of Customer Delight With Special Reference to Ibaco Icecream Shop in Sivakasi

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Abstract

Customer delight is amazing a customer by beyond his or her expectations and it builds a positive emotional reaction. It will indications to word of mouth. However, it has been revealed that mere customer satisfaction does not create brand loyalty nor does it encourage positive word of mouth. Companies need to elevate the relationship from casual to a more intimate relationship of loyalty. The attributes of the product itself does not create any customer delight, it can be accompanied by standard services of the product and by interaction with customers. The interaction is the greatest source of opportunities to create delight as it can be personalized and tailored to the specific needs and wishes of the customer. While coming to the customer delight in IBACO ice cream shop, three stages of consumption process are considered namely pre – purchase, purchase and post-purchase. The factors affected in pre-purchase consumption process are brand image, health issues and suitability. Price, environment and service factors are undertaken in purchasing stage. In post-purchase stage, quality, satisfaction and store experience factors are taken into account. The present research aims to identify the factors of Customer Delight in IBACO Ice cream shop in Sivakasi using non-probability convenience sampling. Chi-square test was used to study the association of pre-purchase, purchase and post-purchase factors which affecting Customer Delight.

Keywords: Customer Delight, Attributes, Ice cream industry

Introduction

In today's world, every company is running in a race to grab the opportunities prevailed in the market and in order to have more profit. As per the Gandhiji quotes 'Every Business depends upon the customer'. So, the company focus on the satisfying the customer by offering products and services in a quality form. As per the TQM, Quality value should be greater than one, which is if the product performance should exceed the expectations of the customer that leads to customer satisfaction. Today, the company has focused on nine dimensions of quality, because no company can give satisfactions on these nine dimensions. The company identified the variations in that dimensions and convert the variations into requirements of the product, thereby new product gets emerge in the market in order to fulfill the gap and also to have better profitability and to bag more market share. These all possible only because of customers. In earlier days, the company has talked about the customer satisfaction.

Consumer loyalty is the impression of the clients towards the execution of the item, in light of the desire and the observation hole the firm can examine the level of variety required to fulfill the clients as far as the administrations. Subsequently it very well may be acknowledged as a parameter for enhancing the execution of the firm. But in today's competitive world, the company is in a situation to think more than the customer in the area that the customers do not think. That area has been identified and giving more with the product which it is unexpected feature in the market. That little extra brings in the delight factor. Delight determines the amount of extra efforts taken by the firms. "Customer delight involves going beyond satisfaction to delivering what can be best described as a pleasurable experience for the client". Enjoyment thusly involves a more grounded feeling and an unexpected physiological state in comparison to fulfillment. The present research has a topical importance in the aggressive situation where brands are attempting to discover techniques to make the above characterized "Charmed Customer" with uncommon reference to the dessert business. The development of the business is driven by accessibility of different seasoned desserts. Subsequently, the frozen yogurt purchasers pay a top notch cost for these items, which thusly expands the income of the market. In any case, the wellbeing concerns related with frozen yogurts limit the market development. The aim of this research is to study about factors that lead to Customer Delight and their association with demographic characteristics of the customer, with special reference to IBACO ice cream shop in Sivakasi.

Three Stages Inconsumption Process Of Ice-Cream

PRE-PURCHASE: Brand image, Health issues & Suitability

Brand image - The customer considers the sort of picture the brand that he will buy delineates. It needs to suit certain grown-up toy, quality and some other individual brand prerequisites that the buyer may have. It is vital that the brand looks after generosity, palatable to the shopper.

Health Issue -The cutting edge purchaser is exceedingly wellbeing cognizant and is getting to be mindful of the rising medical problems and its effects. It is critical that the brand fulfills this need of the purchasers and guarantees wellbeing related gains instead of misfortune.

Suitability – The resultant product should match the taste, flavor and ingredients that is in line with the consumer wants and needs.

Purchase: Price, Environment & Service

Price - Price should be affordable and the product should provide money's worth in terms of quality, quantity and consumer satisfaction as kids also form a main segment of our section a proper care should be given as far as pricing is concerned.

Environment - The environment should be such that the consumer wants to stay there and spent some quality and quantity time.

Service - The service should be fast so that the customer waiting time should be less and leads to their satisfaction and results in formation of good brand image.

Post-Purchase: Quality & Satisfaction

Quality – the quality of the ice cream delivered certainly plays a vital role in determining whether the customer will re purchase the brand or not. The quality and taste of ice cream determines the satisfaction level of the customer and hence plays a vital role in determining his approach towards the product.

Satisfaction - well satisfaction is a holistic picture the total experience of the customer with the brand considering various factors.

Statement of the Problem

The success or failure of market of ice creams, to a certain extent depends on the customer behavior and level of satisfaction derived from the consumption of the product and also the nature and the type of competition in the market. There are different levels of customer delight derived by different set of customers; hence a brief study on the customer delight from the consumption of ice-creams in IBACO ice cream shop in Sivakasi has been selected for the purpose of study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the research work are:

- a) To study the socio-economic profile of the respondents (Gender, Age, Family income etc.).
- b) To determine the most influential factors that motivate customers to remain with the ice cream shop or make them delighted.
- c) To know the association of the influential factors in delighting the customer in the stages of consumption of pre-purchase, purchase and post-purchase.

Research Methodology

The type of research design used for this study is the descriptive research design. Descriptive research is the research for fact finding the major use of descriptive research is explanation of state of affairs, as it exists at present. The research is to identify the factors that motivate the customers to remain with the ice cream shop i.e. IBACO ice cream shop. Both primary and secondary data collection methods have been employed to conduct the research work. Primary data was collected using sample survey which was carried out by means of a self-administered, structured questionnaire. The sampling technique chosen for the research work was non-probability convenience sampling along with the sample size as 60. Chi-square test was used to study the association of demographic variables on factors affecting Customer Delight.

Hypotheses to test the Customer Delight

Based on the findings of the exploratory investigations the following hypotheses were established for the quantitative study:

- H1: Brand image have a positive influences over the customer delightness
- H2: Health issues of IBACO have positively influence the customer delightness.
- H3: Suitability (Taste) have a positive influences over the customer delightness.
- H4: There is a positive relationship between price and customer delightness.
- H5: There is a positive influence of environment on customer delightness.
- H6: There is a positive association between service and customer delightness.
- H7: There is a positive relationship between quality and customer delightness.
- H8: There is a positive influence between satisfaction and customer delightness.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Respondent's Profile

The study of the demographic profile provided the guidance to the researcher to analyse the respondent's perception towards customer delight. The demographic profile like gender, age, income level are depicted in the Table 1

Table 1 Demographic Details of Customer

S.No.	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender		
	Male	32	53.33
	Female	28	46.67
2.	Age Group		
	Below 15 Yrs	6	10
	15-25 yrs	31	51.67
	25-40 yrs	15	25
	Above 40 yrs	8	13.33
3.	Income Level		
	Below Rs 10,000	12	20
	Rs 10,000-Rs 20,000	18	30
	Rs 20,000-Rs 30,000	10	16.67
	Above Rs 30,000	20	33.33

Source: Primary Data

The questionnaire includes a section on customer profile, as one of the various demographic factors to support this research. Information on demographic features is also useful in formulating the ice cream industry marketing strategy. The study of demographic of the respondents provided the guidance to analyse the individual perception towards customer delight. Demographic factors included gender, age and income level. This also helps to generalize the perception of individual responding to questionnaire.

From the Table 1 it can be seen that out of 60 consumers 53.33 per cent consumers are male and 4.67 per cent consumers are female. It is revealed that 51.67 per cent consumers between 15-25 years old, 25 per cent of consumers are between 25-40 year old, 13.33 per cent consumers above 40 years old and 10 per cent consumers below 51year old. 33.33 per cent of consumers are having monthly family income of above Rs. 30,000, 30 per cent of consumers are having income between Rs.10,000 – Rs.20,000, 20 per cent of consumers are having income below Rs.10,000 and 16.67 per cent of consumers are having income between Rs.20,000 – Rs.30,000.

Findings

Table 2 Sample Statistics

Delightness Factors	Sample Size	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pre – Purchase				
Brand Image	60	4.36	.456	.019
Health Issues	60	3.13	.658	.014
Suitability (Taste & Ingredients)	60	3.05	.215	.012
Purchase				
Price	60	1.69	.423	.035
Environment	60	2.89	.254	.023
Service	60	3.92	.204	.016
Post – Purchase				
Quality	60	3.95	.254	.017
Satisfaction	60	3.68	.329	.019

Source: Calculated Data

The descriptive table shows the 60 respondents mean score, standard deviation and standard error against the delight factors. Delight score has been calculated on the basis of Pre-purchase factor, purchase and post purchase factor. It is inferred from the table 2 that the mean score falls in the range of 1.69 to 4.36, which clearly shows that each factor is positively influence the customer delight of the product. As per this analysis, the factor of Brand image. Service, Quality and Satisfaction have shown the mean score of more than 3.5. Followingly, the health issues have secured the mean score of 3.13, Suitability (Taste) has secured the mean score of 3.05 whereas Price and Environment has secured the least mean score of 1.69 and 2.89 in delightness factor. It shows that Price do not have the positive association with the customer delightness factor.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis has been tested with the help of Chi-square statistics. The resultant value of chi-square statistics are depicted in the table 3.

Table 3 Hypotheses Assessment Summary

Hypotheses	Factors	Calculated Value	Table Value	Significant	Result
H 1	Brand image & Customer Delight	25.63	22.59	Highly Significant	Accepted
H 2	Health Issues & Customer Delight	13.87	15.69	Not Significant	Rejected
H 3	Suitability & Customer Delight	21.52	18.34	Highly Significant	Accepted
H 4	Price & Customer Delight	23.63	26.58	Not Significant	Rejected
H 5	Environment & Customer Delight	20.32	17.45	Highly Significant	Accepted
H 6	Service & Customer Delight	19.56	15.32	Highly Significant	Accepted
H 7	Quality & Customer Delight	25.98	21.76	Highly Significant	Accepted
H 8	Satisfaction & Customer Delight	16.52	14.26	Highly Significant	Accepted

Source: Calculated Data

It is inferred from the table 3 that, IBACO has a good brand image among the respondents and it have the positive association with the Customer Delightness. Health issues have not significantly influence the Customer Delightness. Suitability (Taste & Ingredients) also has the positive association with the customer delightness. Price have not significantly influence the customer delightness, thereby it implies that Price of IBACO ice cream seems to be high when compared to the other product prevailed in the market. Environment, Service, quality and Satisfaction have significantly influence the customer delightness.

Suggestions

1. The customer feels that some products and flavor of ice cream may not be in good taste. Hence care should be taken to supply all products and flavors in good taste to increase the customer delightness position.

2. The company may focus and convey the message related to health ingredients used in the icecream while they flash the advertisement in the mass media.
3. Price is one of the major constraint that restrict and promote the sales of IBACO. So, in the shop, there is a need to bring the changes on fixing the price of product(Ice cream) based upon the quantity the customers preferred before the toppings has been made on the icecream.

Conclusion

Satisfaction is a thing of the past. Delight is here to stay and grow. Customer Delight involves going beyond satisfaction to delivering what can be best described as a pleasurable experience for the client. Variables namely Brand Image, price, environment, service, quality and customization, play a vital role in creating Customer delight. It is crystal clear from the study that the current customers are delighted by the Brand image and environment provided by the ice cream shop. Therefore, it is necessary that employees in IBACO ice cream shop should pay high attention to their other variables of the delight to make them more delight.

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